

POTENTIAL USE OF QR CODES FOR PHISHING ATTACKS

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Abstract

This paper highlights the potential vulnerability of QR codes to phishing in the advent of smart devices. The popularity of QR codes has continued to grow since the emergence of smart phones that have cameras, which can also scan and capture encoded QR codes. These phones and scanning APPs provide the means to interact with the physical matrix barcodes. They are extremely popular in marketing, which could be found on billboards, information posters, payment cards, and websites. With this versatility comes a wide range of security issues, which has rarely been investigated. This popularity has propelled this unique study to determine how these codes could be deployed as an attack vector. This study investigated the behavior and potential vulnerabilities of users who scan QR codes in wild. In addition it clearly reiterates the importance of secure Apps and stresses the significance of security awareness as a key solution to potential QR code initiated phishing.

Introduction

Quick response (QR) codes are a type of matrix barcode, which may be used to identify physical objects. QR codes are most commonly used to provide uniform resource locator (URL) addresses that may be attached to physical objects. By reading the QR code with an app that is installed on a smart-phone or other electronic device it is possible to follow the URL to a web page containing information about the physical object (Weir, 2010, pp. 4-23).

QR codes are very useful means of providing additional information about physical objects. However, they are also open to potential abuse by phishing scams. This review will discuss QR technology, how it is used and abused, and potential solutions to QR code phishing.

History of QR codes

QR codes were first developed in the Japanese automotive industry as a method for rapidly identifying the car parts to which they were attached within a factory. This QR code was originally developed to contain four key pieces of information, numeric, alphanumeric, byte/binary, and kanji. This information was used to efficiently identify the item to which it was attached (Kato et al., 2010, pp. 45-73). Because of its fast readability and ease of use the QR code became popular outside the automotive industry. At first it began to replace the standard universal product code (UPC) barcodes that are widely used on commercial products. It was also adopted for use in product tracking, document management, and time tracking.

However, the most popular and widely known use to which QR codes have been adapted is arguably in advertising. QR codes are attached to a wide range of different items that may be used as advertisements. These can include placing QR codes on publicly displayed poster advertisements or on commercial products. Individuals who may be interested in the advertised product are encouraged to scan the QR

code with freely available apps on their smart phones or other mobile devices. Doing so will result in a URL web address being made available and the corresponding web page being displayed on the individual's device (Roebuck, 2011, pp. 230-255).

The uses of QR codes

In addition to their traditional uses in vehicle part tracking and their popular use in commercial advertising QR codes have a wide range of other uses. These can include the following uses.

1. Providing a unique identifier to any type of physical object via a uniform resource identifier (URI).
2. Allowing users to compose email or text messages
3. Directing users to additional information; for example, a poster or presentation summarising a report may include a QR code to link viewers to the complete report.
4. Downloading apps to the user's device.
5. In job advertisements to link potential recruits to additional information about and advertised position.
6. On train or flight tickets to allow rapid identification of a ticketed seat or journey.

Depending on the particular situation QR codes are highly versatile means of linking physical objects with virtual resources and with uniquely identifying physical items. This type of linking of physical objects to virtual information is referred to as "hard-linking" and is being used to provide additional virtual information associated with a wide range of different types of physical objects. Because of this they are rapidly becoming the most popular two-dimensional barcoding system in the world (Duží, 2007, pp. 279-302).

Background of dynamic QR codes

There are two basic types of QR code; static QR codes or dynamic QR codes. Static QR codes always link their users to the same fixed URL web address. Dynamic QR codes link their users to a dynamic web address. The creator or owner of the QR code can change this dynamic web address at any time. This means that the same QR code can be used to link users to a range of different URL web addresses that change over time (Firtman, 2010, pp. 240-271).

Static QR codes require a fixed web address in order to be useful. This means that any future changes that may be made to a website to which a static QR code links have to retain the same address formats that those QR codes expect. If these web addresses are not maintained future users of the QR code may find that they are linked to non-existent web pages (Winter, 2011, pp. 67-79).

Dynamic QR codes solve this problem by providing one fixed short web address, which forwards the user to a second address. The owner of the QR code can change the forwarding address at any time. This means that there is no longer a need to support old QR codes when redesigning websites. However, the initial linking address is often a short format web address. This means that the user of the QR code will not be aware of exactly where the QR code is ultimately sending them. This creates a potential phishing problem for users of dynamic QR codes.

Both static and dynamic QR codes can be created with relative ease for free by anyone using a variety of different online tools. By providing a URL web address individuals can freely and anonymously create either a static or dynamic QR code to link to any URL they wish. The resulting QR code can then be downloaded in a range of different image formats and printed out for any use the QR code creator may wish (Vermaat, 2014, pp. 460-502).

The problem of phishing

Phishing is the process by which an attempt is made to induce an individual into revealing personal information to a malicious third party. This can be achieved by posing as a trusted party or individual in order to trick an individual into revealing details such as passwords or bank account details. Phishing attempts may include sending emails to an individual claiming to be from a trusted party, for example a bank or information technology provider. These emails may go to some considerable length to attempt to convince the recipient that they are genuine. They will then request a password or other personal information (Ciampa, 640, pp. 492-512).

An alternative form of phishing is the creation of phishing websites. These are websites set up to look exactly like a trustworthy website where an individual would typically input sensitive information. For example, websites may be setup to look like an individual's online bank account or email provider (Jakobsson & Myers, 2006, pp. 394-422). Because it is possible to make a phishing website look completely identical to the trusted website it is often very difficult or impossible to tell the two websites apart by looking at their contents. Instead the URL of the website must be inspected to check it matches with that of the trusted website.

Phishing websites often make considerable effort to trick their users into visiting and into trusting the website when they arrive. One such technique is to send individuals an email purporting to be from a trusted party and claiming to have discovered some problem or security breach in an online account (for example, an unexpected cash withdrawal from a bank account). The email will then prompt the recipient to go to their online account and login to check, this will be accompanied by a link to the phishing website (James, 2005, pp. 304-350).

Additionally, the phishing website may use a URL address which is very similar to a trusted web address. This can include using a different domain extension to a trusted address (for example .org instead of .com)

or making a small spelling change in the URL such that the address is different but looks the same at a glance (Blasi, 2009, pp. 51-68). A more recent method that is being used by phishers is to employ QR codes to direct individuals to the phishing website. QR codes may be sent to individuals via email or physical post, or posted in physical locations with other text and images to attempt to encourage individuals to use the QR code to follow the QR code to a phishing website (Alcorn et al., 2014, pp. 460-491).

For example, posters of physical letters may be used to present a phishing QR code to people. This QR code may be embedded within text or images designed to look like a trusted brand. Individuals may be further enticed to follow the QR code by offers or advertisements for free or discounted products. The effectiveness of this form of phishing is further enhanced by the use of dynamic QR codes. Traditionally, phishing websites may be obvious to individuals who are careful to closely inspect the URL in their web browser to check it matches with the expected URL. However, dynamic QR codes will initially display a short form URL (for example, a tiny-URL web address may be used) (Misra & Dubey, 2013, pp. 113-145).

These short form URLs are very commonly used for legitimate reasons such as providing short URL web addresses for use in text messaging or short text communication applications such as Twitter. Therefore, they are widely trusted and even experienced web users may trust them to be re-directing them to the correct web address and not to a phishing website. As a consequence of this, the use of dynamic QR codes for directing people to phishing websites has increased rapidly in recent years. In addition to the potential harm to people who are tricked by the phishing scams these QR codes are used for this also has the effect of reducing general levels of trust in QR codes and their effectiveness as an advertising and information retrieval tool (Beck, 2007, pp. 11-23).

Potential solutions

There are a couple of potential solutions to the growing problem of the use of QR codes for phishing. The first of these is to require creators of both static and dynamic QR codes to register with some authority and provide some personal information when creating the QR code. The second potential solution is to better educate people about the potential dangers associated with following QR codes. Requiring individuals who create QR codes to register their personal details would allow potential tracking of QR codes. For example, if a particular QR code was identified as being commonly used for phishing it would be possible to identify who originally created that QR code. This could potentially reduce the likelihood of QR codes being created for phishing purposes (Nilanjan, 2015, pp. 240-268).

However, there are some problems with this approach. First, there are currently no central authority managing QR codes and an attempt to create one is potentially considerably challenging. Second, part of the attractiveness of QR codes and the reason they are so popular is the speed and ease with which they can be created. Any attempt to reduce phishing with QR codes that makes them less easy to use could

also reduce the popularity and usability of QR codes. Finally, different data protection laws in different countries and regions make the storage and use of personal information of QR code creators potentially legally problematic.

In contrast to this educating people about the potential dangers associated with following QR codes is considerably less problematic. This approach does not reduce the number of phishing attempts being made with QR codes. However, it does have the potential to reduce their effectiveness by ensuring people are less likely to fall for phishing scams (Parno et al., 2005, pp. 20-35).

Educating people about these phishing attempts using QR codes can include requesting they check the final URL address they are directed to. This would also include explanations about what dynamic QR codes are and why they should not automatically trust short form URL web addresses.

Educating people about the risks associated with following QR codes can reduce their vulnerability to phishing scams. However, it does not directly reduce the number of phishing scams. It may also have the effect of reducing general levels of trust in both QR codes and short form URL web addresses. However, it may also indirectly reduce the number of QR codes being used for phishing attempts (Lininger & Vins, 2005, pp. 230-267).

Specifically, by educating people about the potential dangers associated with QR codes it becomes less likely that those people will be tricked by a QR code based phishing attempt. Consequently, this makes the use of QR codes for phishing less attractive and, therefore, reduces the likelihood that QR codes will continue be used for phishing attempts in the future.

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